

SPECIFIC METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZING DUAL EDUCATION
AT THE “INDUSTRY-ENTERPRISE-HIGHLIGHT” LEVEL IN TRAINING ENGINEERS

Kodirov I.N.
Professor of QarDTU

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta’lim muassasalarida muhandislar tayyorlashda “Tarmoq-korxon-oliygoh” darajasida dual ta’limni tashkil etishning xususiy metodologik tamoyillari ishlab chiqilganligi va undan foydalanish yuqori samara berishligi haqida ma’lumotlar berilgan. OTM larda muhandislar tayyorlashda “Tarmoq-korxon-oliygoh” darajasida dual ta’limni joriy etish amaliyotining tahlili uni rivojlantirishning meyoriy-huquqiy bazasini yanada takomillashtirish zarurligi aniqlanganligi bayon qilingan.

Kalit soʻzlar: dual ta’lim, “Tarmoq-korxon-oliygoh”, metodologik tamoyillar, tuzilmaviy daraja, kasbiy faoliyat, dual ta’lim modeli, egallagan malakalari.

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о разработке специальных методических принципов организации дуального образования на уровне «Отрасль-предприятие-вуз» при подготовке инженеров в высших учебных заведениях и высокой эффективности его использования. Анализ практики внедрения дуального образования на уровне «Отрасль-предприятие-вуз» при подготовке инженеров в вузах выявил необходимость дальнейшего совершенствования нормативно-правовой базы его развития.

Ключевые слова: дуальное образование, «Отрасль -предприятие-вуз», методологические принципы, структурный уровень, профессиональная деятельность, модель дуального образования, приобретаемая квалификация.

Annotation. The article presents information on the development of special methodological principles for organizing dual education at the “Industry-enterprise-university” level in the training of engineers in higher education institutions and the high efficiency of its use. An analysis of the practice of introducing dual education at the “Industry-enterprise-university” level in the training of engineers in universities revealed the need for further improvement of the regulatory framework for its development.

Key words: dual education, “Industry-enterprise-university”, methodological principles, structural level, professional activity, dual education model, acquired qualification.

Introduction. In the context of the sustainable development of the world economy, the training of qualified engineering personnel in higher education institutions is an ever-present issue. On 20.06.2024, in a video conference dedicated to the issues of “Priority tasks for the training of personnel in engineering fields and further improvement of the activities of higher education institutions”, the President emphasized that we need to fulfill a number of tasks to train highly qualified engineers, and also gave special instructions that students in all engineering universities should be trained on the basis of dual education and that all operating universities should be assigned an industrial partner based on the “Industry - Enterprise - University” chain.

On January 28, 2024, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting on measures to develop the electric power industry in 2025-2035. It was reported at the meeting that by 2030, it is planned to increase the share of "green" energy in total generation in our country to more than 50 percent. In particular, it is planned to commission 164 megawatts of capacity in 3,000 micro-hydroelectric power

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plants, 750 megawatts of capacity from solar and wind installations, and instructions and a program have been issued to cover at least 50 percent of the roofs of the population and economic entities with solar panels. In addition, an instruction has been given to develop a program to save consumed electricity, natural gas and other heat sources, and to use energy-efficient resources in buildings. The program emphasizes the need to pay special attention to the modernization of enterprises with low energy efficiency and the introduction of new production capacities.

In addition, at a meeting held by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, an order was given to establish an Energy Institute under the Ministry of Energy. It was announced that the institute will have branches in all regions.

As is known, on March 29, 2021, Resolution No. 163 "On measures to organize dual education in the professional education system" and the related Regulation were approved and published by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This, in addition to making a significant contribution to the further development of the use of dual education in our Republic, is of great importance in training qualified engineering personnel.

In the near future, training engineering personnel using the dual education system is a pressing issue in the educational system of all engineering universities operating in order to further increase the production of "green" energy by industry engineers and organize its effective use [1,5-12].

The implementation of dual education in cooperation with universities and manufacturing enterprises based on the "Industry - Enterprise - University" chain and the effective use of it in the educational process by students, as well as the identification of its specific methodological principles, are currently poorly studied and not much research has been conducted in this area, and these issues need to be resolved in a timely manner.

Analysis of the literature on the topic.

Currently, the dual education system is widely used in personnel training in several countries, such as Germany, France, China, the USA, Korea, Russia, Switzerland, Austria, as well as in many Asian countries. The dual education process is considered a joint integration of theory and practice, and it is recognized by scientists as the basis for training qualified personnel in production enterprises[4]. Regarding the dual education system, L.V. Sidakova expresses her opinion that it is "an educational system that involves combining the educational activities of an educational institution with the activities of production enterprises"[2]. It is noted that the dual education system in the training of professionally qualified personnel can be considered as "an educational system that is clearly coordinated between higher vocational education and employer production enterprises, aimed at training specialists with the required level of qualification in a particular profession" [3].

Research methodology.

It is known that the gap between theory and practice in the training of engineering personnel in universities is one of the perennial problems of higher education. This problem has been solved in different ways at different times. The dual education system has proven its effectiveness in solving this problem worldwide. Currently, the dual education system, which is effectively used in the education systems of all countries, is being implemented using the dual education model in the training of future professionals, and good results are being achieved as a result [4-12].

It is known that there are several structural levels of organizing a dual education system in cooperation with industrial enterprises in the training of qualified engineering personnel in higher educational institutions, including:

- organizing dual education at the "Enterprise - University" level;

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- organizing dual education at the "Enterprise - Department" level;
- organizing dual education at the "Enterprise - Laboratory" level;
- organization of dual education at the level of "Industry - Enterprise - University", etc.

We will be able to choose the one we need depending on our goals (Figure 1). In universities, in the process of training qualified engineers, we will have to overcome a number of difficulties in implementing dual education in cooperation with manufacturing enterprises.

Figure 1. Structural levels of dual education organization.

The main difficulties include the following: In many cases, the low level of preparation of students for training at enterprises; the lack of training places at some enterprises; the need to increase the price for the type of product produced at the enterprise and the lack of funds for education in order to

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attract students to study on the basis of dual education; difficulties in forming the content, volume and methods of newly developed dual education programs in cooperation with universities and enterprises; the correct formation of the principles and categories of dual education in accordance with the conditions of production enterprises, the lack of provision of production enterprises (some enterprises, but not all) with the necessary modern equipment, the insufficient level of financing of the dual education process and the need to conduct sufficient events, seminars, trainings, master classes on the procedures for organizing dual education, etc.

In order to assess the effectiveness of the dual education process in training qualified engineers based on dual education and to conduct research effectively, methods such as studying and in-depth analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature on the organization of dual education, mutual evaluation of the content and essence of the materials provided to students in higher education programs, survey, comparison, analysis, and statistical processing were used.

Analysis and results.

As a result of the analysis of the current practice of introducing dual education, it was found that for this, first of all, it is necessary to further improve the existing regulatory and legal framework, to ensure the creation of conditions for the development of dual education in all areas of education.

The organization of dual education in higher education institutions is carried out based on its principles.

Based on the results of comparing dual and traditional training methods, the following specific methodological principles for organizing dual education training for engineers at the "Industry-Enterprise-University" level were developed:

1. In the training of future engineers on the basis of dual education at the level of "Industry-Enterprise-Higher Education", higher education institutions and industrial enterprises are equally responsible for the quality of personnel training.
2. In the training of engineering personnel on the basis of dual education, its structural structure, the content, essence and volume of training conducted during the training process, the number of hours allocated to the training process must correspond to the conditions of industrial enterprises and be organized in accordance with the real needs of enterprises for personnel.
3. Higher education institutions and enterprises must work together in developing and implementing new dual education programs for training engineering specialists.
4. In the organization of the dual education educational process, the volume of production practice should increase to 60-70 percent of the dual curriculum.
5. In the training of engineers in higher educational institutions, it is necessary to ensure that the types of professional activities, unique elements, conditions for implementing dual education, professional competencies formed in the production enterprises themselves correspond to the topics of the materials reflected in the dual education process.
6. The objects, types, elements, conditions for implementation of the professional activities of the engineers being trained, the level of formation of competencies that should be manifested in the professional activities of production enterprises should be covered in detail in the content of the department's disciplines and through newly developed dual education programs.
7. In the training of engineering personnel on the basis of dual education, practical training should be conducted for students with the help of mentors appointed by enterprises, in which it is necessary to ensure the gradual formation of skills in working with the most important objects of the enterprise, and the formation of experience in implementing engineering professional activities in students.

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8. Students' educational and industrial (pre-diploma) internships must be conducted using modern equipment of a production enterprise and be constantly monitored.

In organizing dual education, it is necessary to perform certain organizational and managerial tasks necessary for the effective implementation of the above principles: analyze the conditions for organizing dual education at a higher education institution, the material and technical needs and capabilities of the higher education institution; compile a list of enterprises that correspond to the profile of student training; analyze the conditions for organizing training in the educational and production process at enterprises; agree on plans for the joint implementation of dual education; conclude cooperation agreements based on social partnership with the higher education institution for the entire period of students' study; develop tripartite cooperation agreements between students, higher education institutions and enterprises and conclude and approve the agreements to be implemented between them. If it is not possible to fully provide training for the formation of all types of professional activities of engineers being trained at a production enterprise, then ensure the conclusion of agreements with several enterprises; To organize the internships of university professors and teachers on the basis of partner specialized enterprises; to organize the activities of teachers assigned by the employer production enterprises conducting internships, to involve them in teaching academic subjects or certain sections of academic subjects, depending on the formation of their professional pedagogical skills and needs (if necessary, to organize special training seminars for them).

The results of the conducted scientific research showed that the successful organization of dual education in the training of engineers at the level of "Industry-Enterprise-Higher Education" is determined by the diversity of developed specific methodological principles, the content and essence of the educational and methodological complexes of subjects, the balanced conduct of theoretical and practical classes for students, and the coordination of the formation of dual education in them and the solution of problems in its further development.

Was the organization and testing of dual education at the "Industry-Enterprise-University" level effective? What difficulties were encountered in this?

In the joint organization of dual education at the "Industry-Enterprise-University" level, although the direct employers needed trained and qualified personnel, they did not want to take on the responsibility of teaching personnel who would work at the enterprise in the future. In the joint organization of dual education at the "Industry-Enterprise-University" level, the lack of regulatory and legal documents and difficulties in adapting newly developed dual education curricula to the business activities of the enterprise were identified.

If employers cannot forecast their personnel needs for the next 3-5 years, they do not have the ability to assess the ratio of personnel training costs and benefits from them, it will be difficult to involve them in the training process based on dual education. If higher education institutions help enterprises solve forecasting problems, enterprises can easily overcome these difficulties and ensure that their personnel needs are met. It should be noted that if employers do not show interest in solving the difficulties of training professional workers as partners with higher education institutions and actively participate in the process of education, it is impossible to give a 100% guarantee that the problems of interaction between higher education institutions and enterprises and the effectiveness of the introduction of dual education will be high and successful.

Conclusions

1. Eight specific methodological principles of dual education for the organization of dual education at the level of “Industry-Enterprise-Higher Education” have been developed. Reliance on the specific methodological principles developed in the organization of dual education is its distinctive feature.
2. The results of a special survey among graduating students, professors and teachers of higher education institutions and industrial enterprises have been analyzed. It turned out that in the process of training students on the basis of dual education, it was found that the acquired qualifications, practically formed skills and acquired experience were carried out in a dual education environment based on the newly developed dual education programs. It was found that the educational materials that students need to study are in line with the requirements of production enterprises and can fully meet their requirements.
4. Organizing dual education at the “Industry-Enterprise-University” level in the training of engineers is more difficult than at other structural levels, however, according to the results of testing, it was found to be more effective than others. An analysis of the practice of introducing dual education at the “Industry-Enterprise-University” level revealed the need to further improve the regulatory and legal framework for its development.

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